

NODES

Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

MODEL OF A HYDROLOGICAL RESPONSE

SPOKE 4 – Digital innovation toward sustainable mountain

DELIVERABLE DN.11

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Contents

GLOSSARY	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
A) STUDY AREA AND DATA	5
HYDRO-METEOROLOGICAL DATA.....	6
GEOGRAPHICAL DATABASE.....	7
B) METHODOLOGY	9
OVERVIEW OF THE DREAM MODEL.....	9
DAILY-SCALE MODEL CONFIGURATION.....	12
HOURLY-SCALE MODEL CONFIGURATION.....	13
C) RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	14
DAILY-SCALE SIMULATION RESULTS.....	14
HOURLY-SCALE SIMULATION RESULTS.....	17
D) METEOROLOGICAL NETWORK UPDATE	20
E) CONCLUSIONS	22
F) REFERENCES	22

Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The growing frequency and intensity of extreme hydro-meteorological events—exacerbated by climate change—has underscored the need for advanced, high-resolution tools for hydrological risk prediction and management. This deliverable presents a comprehensive modeling framework aimed at improving the simulation and forecasting of flood events in the Corleto Fiumarella basin, a small, mountainous catchment located in Basilicata, Southern Italy.

The core of the study is the application of the physically based, semi-distributed DREAM model capable of operating at both daily and hourly time scales. DREAM incorporates spatial heterogeneity with detailed digital elevation models, land use classifications, and soil texture data. Calibration and validation were carried out using long-term in-situ observations and a multi-criteria approach, including single and multi-objective strategies supported by genetic algorithms.

A comprehensive hydro-meteorological monitoring network—active since 2002—provided high-resolution datasets, including meteorological variables, soil moisture measurements (via TDR probes), and river discharge. These data together with spatially distributed soil and land cover parameters integrated using pedotransfer functions, informed the calibration and evaluation of DREAM across a range of flow regimes.

At the daily scale, DREAM effectively reproduced long-term water balance components, while the hourly configuration captured short-term flood dynamics, particularly during high-intensity events. At the hourly scale, the analysis of 12 flood events highlighted the model's strengths in simulating both moderate and extreme conditions, with room for refinement during high-uncertainty scenarios.

This integrated modeling and monitoring system offers a replicable and adaptable methodology for hydrological forecasting in mountainous regions. Its application holds significant potential for operational flood prediction and water management. In this context, the integration of high-resolution weather radar systems (e.g., WR-10X) is expected to further enhance the spatiotemporal accuracy of precipitation inputs, strengthening model performance and early warning capabilities.

A) Study area and data

The catchment area of the Fiumarella di Corleto, located in the Basilicata region of southern Italy, covers approximately 32.5 km² and falls within the Sauro River basin, a sub-fluent of the Agri. Within it, an experimental sub-basin has been identified on the right slope (0.65 km²) for detailed analysis of small-scale hydrological processes. The basin features significant elevation variability (average 1050 m a.s.l.), influencing rainfall distribution and surface/subsurface runoff. The climate is sub-humid Mediterranean, with annual rainfall around 720 mm, concentrated in autumn and winter, and large seasonal temperature variation.

Geologically and pedologically, the basin has two distinct slopes: the left, with clay and marl soils under mainly agricultural use; and the right, with arenaceous and conglomeratic formations and predominant forest cover. These differences significantly affect infiltration and runoff generation, resulting in heterogeneous hydrological behavior. The forested side shows greater infiltration and water retention, while the agricultural areas are characterized by quicker surface runoff. These contrasts were parameterized in the DREAM model using distributed soil maps from pedological surveys, complemented by pedotransfer functions to estimate field capacity, saturation, and hydraulic conductivity.

Since September 2002, the basin has been equipped with an advanced monitoring network to study hydrological processes and improve flood-forecasting capabilities (Figure 1). The network includes:

- A meteorological station on the right slope measuring atmospheric variables and supporting water balance analysis;
- A hydrometric station at the basin outlet, equipped with a tipping-bucket rain gauge and ultrasonic level sensor, for real-time discharge estimation and flood dynamics analysis;
- A rain gauge on the left slope with a tipping-bucket mechanism for improved spatial rainfall characterization;
- A soil moisture monitoring system in the sub-basin with 22 TDR probes at various depths, enabling analysis of soil water content and improving hydrological model calibration;
- An Odyssey probe with a Teflon cable, installed in a calm tank under a manhole, calibrated in the lab, to measure water level in the sub-basin.

Figure 1. Location of the experimental basin and sub-basin of “Fiumarella di Corleto”.

Hydro-meteorological data

The hydrological dataset used for the modeling was derived from a monitoring network that collects the main meteorological and hydrological variables in real time, with high temporal resolution (Figure 2). Precipitation, measured by three rain gauge stations distributed throughout the basin, is recorded every ten minutes. These data were subsequently aggregated at both hourly and daily scales to match the temporal configurations required by the model. Precipitation data were spatially distributed using the Thiessen polygon method, converting point measurements into distributed inputs to enhance the simulation of hydrological processes and runoff dynamics. For the experimental sub-basin, the entire area falls within the influence of a single station, thus no spatial interpolation was necessary.

River discharge was estimated from sub-hourly measurements of hydrometric levels, collected by ultrasonic sensor for the main basin and odyssey sensor for the sub-basin installed at the hydraulic control points. These measurements were converted into flow rates using calibrated rating curves specific to the basin and the sub-basin.

The resulting discharge time series were then aggregated to hourly and daily scales, calculating averages consistent with the required temporal resolution.

Air temperature, measured on an hourly basis, was processed to derive daily maximum, minimum and average values. These parameters are essential for calculating potential evapotranspiration and for estimating the phase of precipitation (rain or snow), as they directly influence snow accumulation and melt processes.

Soil moisture content was monitored using TDR probes installed in the sub-basin at two representative depths (30 cm and 60 cm). These data were utilized to reconstruct soil moisture dynamics over time, aiming to determine the amount of water present in the soil prior to each rainfall event and to improve the estimation of the initial conditions in the water balance.

Figure 2. Main hydrological and meteorological-climatic input variables.

Geographical database

The geomorphological dataset provides the spatial information required for the physical characterization of the basin and the distributed parameterization of the hydrological model (Figure 3). To enable a detailed analysis of hydrological processes, thematic maps were developed,

including lithology, land use, slope, aspect, and soil texture. A spatial resolution of 80 meters was used for the main basin and 5 meters for the experimental sub-basin, ensuring accurate representation of key physical attributes such as hydraulic conductivity, water retention capacity, and surface roughness. The thematic maps used include:

- Digital Elevation Model (DEM);
- Percentages of sand, clay, and organic matter;
- Soil type classification;
- Manning's roughness coefficient;
- Land use/land cover;
- Effective soil depth.

These datasets were derived from field surveys, regional soil and land cover maps and satellite-based remote sensing (e.g., NDVI), ensuring a detailed spatial resolution suitable for the DREAM model grid. All layers were clipped to match the study area and subsequently rasterized, ensuring spatial consistency with the modeling domain. Each pixel was assigned a representative value for the corresponding variable, thereby creating a matrix of distributed inputs.

Specific reclassification procedures were applied to land use and soil texture classes to match the model input formats, while Manning's coefficients were assigned based on the dominant land cover type per pixel, ensuring an accurate representation of surface roughness variability within the basin.

The basin's pedology was derived from the studies of Romano and Palladino, 2002 and Romano and Santini, 1997 that investigated the main soil-land units of the basin through field campaigns and laboratory measurements. For the zones without available information, the data was integrated with a land system map of the whole Agri basin, whose soil classification was realised according to the HYPRES (HYdraulic PProperties of European Soil) database that also defines hydraulic characteristics. The soil characterisation is articulated in the following physical quantities: soil texture (according to the USDA classification), organic carbon, thickness. Through the application of pedotransfer functions and automated processing codes, the input data were transformed into key hydrological variables required by the model: saturated hydraulic conductivity, field capacity, wilting point, residual water content, evapotranspiration parameters, and surface roughness. Pedotransfer functions (PTFs) were applied following Saxton et al. (1986) formulations, calibrated locally to reflect the dominant textural classes observed in the field. The use of distributed PTF-derived parameters allowed DREAM to spatially differentiate infiltration capacities and soil moisture dynamics across heterogeneous basin sectors.

Figure 3. Main geomorphological input maps.

B) Methodology

Overview of the DREAM Model

The hydrological simulation approach adopted in this study is based on the use of the physically based, spatially distributed model DREAM (Distributed model for Runoff, Evapotranspiration, and Antecedent soil Moisture simulation), which allows for a detailed representation of the basin's hydrological response under varying meteorological and land surface conditions (Manfreda et al., 2005).

DREAM simulates key hydrological processes such as canopy interception, infiltration, soil water storage, overland flow, subsurface lateral flow, baseflow, and evapotranspiration. The model structure is built to account for spatial heterogeneity by discretizing the catchment into elementary computational units derived from the DEM, and assigning variable soil and land use properties to each grid cell.

The modeling framework has been applied at two temporal scales, daily and hourly, building on the same physical principles but adapting configuration and processes representation to the different temporal resolutions. Both applications integrate spatial datasets and meteorological forcing, but are tailored to address distinct modeling objectives. The following scheme illustrates the internal logic of the DREAM hydrological model. It conceptually describes the soil water balance and the generation of different runoff components (surface, subsurface, and groundwater), based on threshold values and redistribution mechanisms (Figure 4).

Figure 4. DREAM model Flow Chart.

After setting the geomorphological inputs, the model starts from the analysis of total rainfall (P_{tot}), part of which is intercepted by vegetation and evaporates. Interception is represented as a storage bucket with a maximum capacity w_{sc} , which is proportional to the Leaf Area Index (LAI). Following the formulation by Dickinson (1984):

$$w_{sc} = 0.2LAI$$

where LAI is defined as a function of its maximum potential value (Milella et al., 2012).

The water balance on the interception is governed by the equation:

$$\frac{\Delta w_c}{\Delta t} = p_v - e_c$$

where w_c is the water stored on the vegetation, p_v is the incident rainfall, and e_c is the evaporation from the canopy. Thus, the net rainfall P_{net} reaching the ground is computed as:

$$P_{net,t} = P_{tot} - Int$$

where P_{tot} is the total precipitation, and Int is the intercepted amount, i.e. the increase in canopy storage.

Residual net rainfall can infiltrate into the soil, conditioned by soil saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s) and antecedent soil moisture, through the occurrence of conditions:

$$P_{net,t} > K_s$$

If this threshold is exceeded, the infiltration behavior is determined through the formula adopted by De Smedt et al. (2000):

$$Infiltration = \min \left(S_{max} - S_t, P_{net,t} \left(1 - C_p \left(\frac{S_t}{S_{max}} \right)^\alpha \right) \right)$$

where C_p is the potential runoff coefficient, and α is runoff attenuation coefficient. Consequently, the net rainfall excess is determined as:

$$P_{net,t+1} = P_{net,t} - Infiltration$$

At this point, flow branches off in different directions depending on the level of soil saturation:

If excess water fails to infiltrate, excess rainfall is generated that can accumulate in surface depressions and contribute to direct runoff.

If the soil becomes saturated ($S_t > S_c$), the process of deep percolation to the water table is triggered and is governed by the expression:

$$RG_t = K_s \left(\frac{S_t}{S_{max}} \right)^\beta$$

with $\beta = (2+3m)/m$ and m is the pore-size index distribution (Eagleson, 1978)

When saturation exceeds a maximum threshold ($S_t > S_{max}$), subsurface flow is generated due to excess saturation, which feeds subsurface runoff. Some water may also contribute to subsurface lateral flow. So the model redistributes the subsurface runoff cell by cell using the equation:

$$RS_{t,j} = \left(\frac{W_j \sum_{i=1}^{N(t)} \max[c(S_{t,i} - S_{c,i}), 0]}{\sum_{i=1}^{N(t)} W_i} \right) - \max[c(S_{t,i} - S_{c,i}), 0]$$

where $RS_{t,j}$ is the subsurface lateral flow in a j -cell, W_i is the wetness Index at cell i , $S_{t,i}$ is the soil water content and $S_{c,i}$ is the soil water content at field capacity, and $N(t)$ is the number of cells.

The total simulated runoff (Qh) is thus the sum of:

- Direct runoff from excess rainfall
- Contribution from groundwater
- Subsurface runoff

The total hourly runoff at the basin closure section is obtained by summing the contributions from each cell, each of which is delayed by its own runoff time. This propagation process is described by the equation:

$$Qh = \sum_{d=1}^{\tau_{max}} R_t - f_t \quad (f_t = d)$$

where f_t represents the time it takes for the water to reach the outlet, and τ_{max} denotes the maximum runoff time in the basin.

The rainfall-runoff transformation at each time step is controlled by soil hydraulic properties estimated through pedotransfer functions, while the flow routing component uses a linear reservoir approach differentiated by surface and subsurface contributions.

The DREAM model was applied at both daily and hourly temporal scales to capture the hydrological behavior of the basin across different time horizons. The daily-scale configuration was employed to assess long-term hydrological dynamics, with a focus on the temporal evolution of water balance components such as soil moisture, effective precipitation, and evapotranspiration. This setup is suitable for evaluating seasonal patterns, interannual variability, and cumulative water storage processes within the basin, offering a broader view of the catchment's behavior over extended time periods. Snow accumulation and melt, especially at higher elevations, were explicitly considered in the DREAM model using a degree-day snowmelt approach calibrated on local temperature data. On the other hand, the hourly scale configuration was implemented to simulate the short-term response of the basin, particularly under conditions of intense and rapidly varying rainfall events. This finer resolution enhances the ability of the model to reproduce detailed processes such as infiltration-excess runoff, dynamic changes in soil moisture, and the formation and routing of flood hydrographs. The hourly scale is especially valuable in representing flash flood phenomena and assessing the hydrological impact of high-frequency meteorological variability.

Daily-scale model configuration

The daily configuration of the DREAM model was applied to simulate the long-term hydrological behavior of the Fiumarella di Corleto basin during the 2003–2011 period. This setup enabled the analysis of key processes such as runoff generation, seasonal soil moisture dynamics, baseflow persistence, and event-based runoff ratios, providing valuable insights into the basin's response under varying climatic conditions.

For this purpose, a dedicated calibration framework was implemented, testing three different calibration strategies to reproduce the observed daily discharge at the basin outlet (Figure 5):

- Approach A: Single-objective calibration based solely on total runoff;
- Approach B: Multi-objective calibration on both total runoff and baseflow separation;
- Approach C: Multi-objective calibration including total runoff, baseflow, and annual water balance closure.

Each approach was implemented under four different parameterization configurations:

- Configuration 1: Uniform parameters across the basin;
- Configuration 2: Spatially distributed parameters from pedotransfer functions;
- Configuration 3: Spatial distribution plus calibrated scaling factors;

- Configuration 4: Spatial distribution plus scaling and observed baseflow recession constants (K_g).

Figure 5. Calibration framework proposed.

An evolutionary Genetic Algorithm (GA) was used to optimize the model parameters for each calibration approach and configuration. Model performance was assessed using a combination of statistical indicators: the Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and the Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE), providing a comprehensive evaluation of both accuracy and reliability.

Moreover, a comparison with three grouped flow indicators was performed in order to analyse the model performance with respect to different flow conditions: low (LQ), medium (MQ), and high (HQ). These indicators were selected as reported in the works of Sikorska-Senoner, 2021 and Gnann et al., 2021.

Hourly-scale model configuration

The hourly-scale configuration was designed to capture short-term hydrological responses during high-intensity rainfall events. Runoff routing is performed using a dual linear reservoir approach, distinguishing between surface and subsurface contributions (Perrini et al., 2024).

The performance of the DREAM model at hourly-scale was assessed through the simulation of 12 flood events recorded between 2006 and 2022, in both the main basin and the experimental sub-basin. The selected events span a wide range of hydrometeorological conditions, including moderate to intense rainfall episodes, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of the model's predictive capabilities.

Model calibration followed an event-specific and physically based approach, inspired by recent methodologies that emphasize minimizing equifinality by limiting the number of adjustable parameters to those with direct hydrological relevance. Calibrated parameters included the runoff attenuation coefficient, the field capacity threshold for infiltration activation, and percentage adjustments to saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ks). Parameter ranges were constrained within physically plausible limits, informed by field measurements (e.g. TDR soil moisture data) and PTF-derived estimates.

Calibration was carried out manually through an iterative process without the use of automatic optimization algorithms. This approach ensured a consistent alignment between model behavior and observed catchment dynamics for each event. Model performance was evaluated using multiple criteria: KGE, NSE, RMSE, and relative error in peak discharge estimation. This configuration strategy was instrumental in accurately capturing a wide range of flood behaviors, from moderate events to more complex and uncertain hydrometeorological conditions.

C) Results and Discussion

Daily-scale simulation results

The application of the DREAM model at daily scale over the Fiumarella di Corleto basin provided a detailed understanding of the hydrological dynamics of the area and demonstrated the effectiveness of using a physically-based distributed modeling approach combined with multi-objective calibration strategies.

The simulation covered a multi-year period, from 2004 to 2011, allowing the model to be evaluated under a wide range of hydro-meteorological conditions, from dry years to exceptionally wet periods. A warm-up phase during 2003 was used to initialize soil moisture and groundwater states, ensuring consistency in long-term simulations.

Figure 6 illustrates the performance of the DREAM model during the full simulation period. In panel (a), the mirror hydrograph compares recorded and simulated discharge on a daily basis, highlighting the model's ability to capture both the timing and intensity of peak flows, as well as low-flow conditions. The results show a strong agreement throughout the simulation period, including both the calibration (2004–2007) and validation (2008–2011) phases. Panel (b) presents the flow duration curves for both observed and simulated discharge. The close overlap between the two curves across the entire range of flow conditions—especially in the intermediate and low-flow regimes—demonstrates the model's robustness and reliability in reproducing the full spectrum of hydrological behaviors.

Figure 6. Comparison between the simulated and recorded daily streamflow for the “Fiumarella of Corleto” basin (a) and flow duration curves (b) of the entire period.

The calibration process, conducted separately for Approaches A, B, and C, clearly demonstrated the benefits of enhancing the physical realism of model parameterization and implementing multi-objective calibration strategies. Among the tested setups, Configuration 4—combining spatially distributed parameters with scaling factors and incorporating observed recession constants (Kg)—consistently yielded the best performance across all approaches.

During the validation period (2008–2011), the model achieved strong results: RMSE was reduced to approximately 0.25 m³/s, NSE reached 0.67, and KGE peaked at 0.82. These metrics indicate that the model reliably reproduced daily flow dynamics, accurately capturing both the timing and magnitude of discharge peaks and recessions.

Notably, multi-objective calibration—especially with Approach C—led to significant improvements over single-objective methods, particularly in simulating baseflow dynamics and seasonal flow variability. This is visually supported by Figures 7–9: Configuration 4 not only shows higher median performance values across all metrics but also reduced variability during validation, indicating greater robustness and stability. Approach C, which includes water balance constraints, delivered the most consistent and accurate results.

Detailed hydrograph comparisons confirmed that the use of distributed parameterization and recession constants improved the model’s ability to simulate both rapid responses to rainfall and slow drainage during dry periods. Accurate representation of antecedent soil moisture, supported by field measurements, played a key role in enhancing runoff simulations. At the annual scale, water balance closure errors remained below 5% in the best-performing configurations, underscoring the physical plausibility and internal consistency of the simulations. Additionally, evapotranspiration estimates followed expected seasonal trends for a Mediterranean sub-humid climate, and soil water storage dynamics were realistically reproduced, aligning well with TDR observations.

Figure 7. Box plots of RMSE, NSE, KGE values considering configuration A.

Figure 8. Box plots of RMSE, NSE, KGE values considering configuration B.

Figure 9. Box plots of RMSE, NSE, KGE values considering configuration C.

An important aspect of the validation phase involved assessing the DREAM model's ability to reproduce key hydrological signatures associated with different flow regimes. The results demonstrate that the model performs consistently well across low, medium, and high flows, with improvements particularly evident under multi-objective calibration strategies.

For low flows (LQ), the relative error was significantly reduced under multi-objective setups, confirming the model's enhanced capability to simulate baseflow-dominated periods and drought conditions. For medium flows (MQ)—crucial for water resource planning and ecological flow maintenance—the simulations showed strong reliability with low bias. In the case of high flows (HQ), while inherently more variable due to the rapid dynamics of storm-driven runoff, the model still achieved satisfactory accuracy with acceptable error margins.

Table 1 summarizes the model's average relative error for each flow regime, highlighting the most effective parameter configuration. Notably, Configuration 4 (spatially distributed parameters with PTF and observed recession constants) consistently outperformed others, especially in simulating low and medium flows. High-flow performance remained robust across Configurations 2 to 4, underscoring the importance of including spatial detail and physically meaningful parameters when modeling flash flood behavior.

Flow Regime	Metrics	Best Configuration	Average Relative Error (%)
LQ (Low Flow)	BFI, Low Q Duration, Baseflow Magnitude	Configuration 4 (PTF + Kg)	10–15%
MQ (Medium Flow)	Mean Flow, Skewness, Total Runoff Ratio	Configuration 4 (PTF + Kg)	15–20%
HQ (High Flow)	Event Runoff Ratio, High Flow Duration, Flashiness Index	Configuration 2–4	25–30%

Table 1. Average relative error of the DREAM model across different flow regimes (LQ, MQ, HQ).

Hourly-scale simulation results

The DREAM model showed a generally good ability to simulate short-term flood dynamics at hourly resolution, as evidenced by the performance metrics in Table 2 and the hydrograph comparisons in Figure 11.

In the main basin, NSE and KGE values ranged from 0.27 to 0.96, reflecting an overall positive model performance across varying hydrometeorological conditions. The event-specific calibration strategy, supported by distributed input data and TDR-based soil moisture measurements where available, proved effective in capturing both the timing and magnitude of peak discharges, especially for moderate events. For example, Event 3 (20-02-2007) was

simulated with excellent accuracy (NSE = 0.96, KGE = 0.96, relative error = 4.78%), confirming the model's reliability under well-observed conditions. In contrast, complex events such as Event 7 (24-11-2019) or Event 11 (18-02-2011) revealed larger discrepancies, particularly in peak flow estimates—highlighting the sensitivity of model outputs to spatial rainfall variability and initial soil moisture conditions. Despite these challenges, relative errors for most events remained within acceptable bounds (typically <20% for moderate events).

In the sub-basin, the model maintained reasonable performance despite the smaller scale and increased sensitivity to localized inputs. Here, NSE values ranged from -0.40 to 0.88, with particularly good simulations for Event 1 (01-12-2013) and Event 9 (03-05-2018). Cases of underperformance (e.g., Event 6) emphasize the critical role of accurate soil moisture initialization and precipitation data quality, especially in steep headwater catchments.

<i>Basin events</i>											
<i>Evento n°</i>	<i>data</i>	<i>Duration</i> [h]	<i>Pgross</i> [mm]	<i>A.S.M.</i>	<i>Lag-Time</i> [h]	<i>Qoss</i> [mc/s]	<i>Qsim</i> [mc/s]	<i>err [%]</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>KGE</i>	<i>NS</i>
1	01/12/2013	64	125.48	θ_c	2.0	41.77	34.70	16.93	3.03	0.83	0.84
2	23/01/2007	21	41.30	θ_c	8.5	11.82	8.86	25.08	1.34	0.83	0.81
3	20/02/2007	26	36.34	θ_c	3	11.41	11.96	4.78	0.68	0.96	0.96
4	29/03/2007	39	17.87	θ_c	2.5	7.48	8.09	8.23	0.42	0.90	0.92
5	30/01/2015	39	45.77	θ_c	3.5	9.26	7.61	17.85	0.97	0.83	0.86
6	23/05/2018	9	29.37	θ_c	1	23.30	22.06	5.31	2.06	0.75	0.71
7	24/11/2019	48	51.69	θ_c	3	6.75	10.39	53.93	1.54	0.24	0.41
8	31/01/2014	97	97.01	θ_c	2.5	15.99	12.68	20.68	2.20	0.65	0.51
9	03/05/2018	23	31.40	θ_c	1	2.08	1.65	20.54	0.33	0.53	0.27
10	22/01/2009	30	28.30	θ_c	2.5	19.54	11.89	39.19	1.78	0.50	0.68
11	18/02/2011	39	45.77	θ_c	3	29.08	21.72	25.29	2.56	0.75	0.90
12	20/03/2007	13	31.72	θ_c	5.5	7.96	6.92	13.10	1.16	0.53	0.50

<i>Subbasin events</i>											
<i>Evento n°</i>	<i>data</i>	<i>Duration</i> [h]	<i>Pgross</i> [mm]	<i>TDR</i> cmc/cmc	<i>Lag-Time</i> [h]	<i>Qoss</i> [mc/s]	<i>Qsim</i> [mc/s]	<i>err [%]</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>KGE</i>	<i>NS</i>
1	01/12/2013	64	122.52	0.374	1.5	0.41	0.48	15.41	0.04	0.87	0.80
2	23/01/2007	21	41.20	0.209	4.5	0.69	0.57	17.69	0.23	0.40	-0.04
3	20/02/2007	22	28.80	0.114	3	0.33	0.33	1.81	0.06	0.68	0.57
4	29/03/2007	22	18.00	0.324	5	0.29	0.33	14.34	0.04	0.73	0.45
5	30/01/2015	39	55.80	0.181	7.5	0.82	0.54	34.30	0.10	0.63	0.79
6	23/05/2018	9	30.60	0.345	4.5	0.61	0.75	24.48	0.25	0.38	-0.40

7	24/11/2019	18	42.20	0.05	5	0.67	0.61	7.81	0.09	0.70	0.87
8	31/01/2014	97	104.00	0.262	2.5	0.36	0.26	28.12	0.06	0.61	0.49
9	03/05/2018	21	30.60	0.252	4.5	0.51	0.50	2.95	0.05	0.77	0.88
10	22/01/2009	29	39.60	0.304	6.5	0.62	0.55	11.19	0.12	0.66	0.53
11	18/02/2011	21	53.60	0.242	5.5	0.63	0.55	12.70	0.09	0.78	0.74
12	20/03/2007	13	35.40	0.352	2	0.57	0.41	28.85	0.09	0.60	0.54

Table 2. Key statistics of observed and simulated flood events.

Figure 11 illustrates selected hydrographs, showing the model's ability to replicate the shape, timing, and peak of the flood wave. Where runoff components were disaggregated, DREAM offered plausible internal process representations, reinforcing the coherence of the modeling structure. Overall, the results confirm the model's robustness and adaptability in simulating hourly flood events. However, they also underscore the need for improved spatial resolution of precipitation inputs and careful calibration in data-scarce scenarios. The event-based calibration approach proved to be a practical compromise between process realism and computational efficiency, supporting DREAM's application in operational forecasting for small mountainous basins.

Figure 9. Overview of the simulated flood events, showing the comparison between observed and modeled hydrographs across different rainfall events.

D) Meteorological Network Update

As part of the ongoing modernization of the hydro-meteorological monitoring network within the Fiumarella di Corleto basin, a key innovation involves the planned deployment of a mini weather radar system (WR-10X). This single-polarization radar represents a strategic

enhancement aimed at improving the spatial and temporal resolution of precipitation data, which are critical inputs for hydrological modeling, especially in small and fast-responding mountain catchments. Unlike traditional point-based measurements from rain gauges, weather radar provides continuous spatial coverage of rainfall fields, enabling the real-time detection and quantification of precipitation across the entire basin with high temporal frequency. The WR-10X system, with a maximum effective range of 108 km, is capable of generating high-resolution rainfall estimates that can capture localized and short-duration convective events often missed by sparse ground-based sensors. These events are particularly relevant in steep basins where flash flood dynamics are sensitive to the spatial distribution and intensity of rainfall. To ensure optimal performance, a preliminary site suitability analysis was conducted, considering factors such as elevation, orographic exposure, and potential for external signal interference. The trade-off between radar coverage and data quality was carefully evaluated: higher elevation sites offer broader spatial visibility but may introduce beam overshooting or spurious signals; conversely, low-lying sites ensure better near-ground detection but limit the radar's coverage area. The selected installation point reflects a balance between these constraints, maximizing both radar effectiveness and hydrological relevance. Currently, the WR-10X radar system has been fully assembled, and functional tests are underway (Figure 10). These include:

- Installation and verification of communication and power interfaces (RTX, TLC rail, DC converter);
- Calibration of elevation offset detection and azimuth/elevation tracking systems;
- Functional testing of radar movement protocols and data transmission components.

The radar's integration marks a significant step forward in the transition toward a high-resolution, spatially-aware hydrological monitoring network, paving the way for more accurate flood prediction and water resource management under increasingly variable climatic conditions.

Figure 11. Laboratory functional testing and geographic location of the WR-10X weather radar over the study basin.

E) Conclusions

This work explores a methodology for the application and validation of the DREAM physically-based, semi-distributed hydrological model on the Fiumarella di Corleto basin, demonstrating its reliability for hydrological simulations across both daily and hourly time scales. The integration of detailed field observations, high-resolution spatial datasets, and advanced multi-criteria calibration strategies enabled the DREAM model to accurately reproduce the main hydrological processes of a small, fast-responding Mediterranean mountain basin. The model achieved high predictive capabilities across a multi-year period (2004–2011), with satisfactory values of NSE, KGE, and RMSE. Multi-objective calibration strategies, particularly those integrating baseflow dynamics and annual water balance, significantly improved model realism and stability across different flow regimes (low, medium, and high flows). At the hourly scale, the model was capable of simulating 12 selected flood events with a wide range of hydrological conditions. While DREAM successfully captured moderate events with high accuracy, larger uncertainties emerged during extreme rainfall events, emphasizing the challenges of short-term forecasting under intense hydrometeorological conditions. Event-specific calibrations, supported by soil moisture data and pedotransfer function estimates, enhanced the model's flexibility and adaptability. The results show that the DREAM model is a suitable tool for flood forecasting, hydrological risk assessment, and water resource management in small mountainous catchments. High-resolution radar data could provide a more accurate representation of the spatial and temporal variability of precipitation, thereby reducing forecast uncertainties and enhancing model reliability under rapidly evolving meteorological conditions.

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